

Memo

The ODISSEI Portal & The DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities

Connections, commonalities, differences, and future directions

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Content

INTRODUCTION.....	3
BACKGROUND.....	4
ODISSEI Portal.....	4
DANS Data Station SSH.....	4
CONNECTION BETWEEN THE ODISSEI PORTAL AND THE DANS DATA STATION SSH...	6
Commonalities and differences.....	6
DEVELOPMENTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS.....	8
Development and maintenance	8
Distinguished look and feel.....	8
The role of the data providers	9
The special role of CBS.....	10
IN SUMMARY	11

Introduction

This document outlines the current state of the ODISSEI Portal and the DANS Data Station for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and their connection.

We first provide background of both applications and then describe their connection, outlining commonalities and differences.

Finally, we discuss the maintenance of both applications and possible directions for future developments of the Portal and the Data Station. The section on future directions is not exhaustive or directive, but merely outlines developments which seem possible at the current point in time. Based on this initial document and feedback that we receive (e.g. from the ODISSEI Management Board), a proposal for the future will be created.

Background

ODISSEI Portal

The [ODISSEI Portal](#) is being developed as part of the [ODISSEI roadmap project](#) which started in 2020. It was envisioned as the place where (Dutch) social science researchers can easily find and request access to datasets from a range of different (Dutch) data providers. Rather than visiting each data provider's repositories or services separately, the Portal could provide one central point for finding relevant datasets.

The Portal has been envisioned to be closely linked to existing infrastructure, in particular the data discovery services of DANS.

As the services of DANS and the wider community keep developing further (e.g. through the launch of the DANS Data Station and the development of SANE), the vision of the Portal, its position and functionality keeps evolving accordingly.

The first version of the prototype of the ODISSEI Portal was released [in September 2022](#) and multiple new releases have been done since. The latest release was [in October 2023](#) and a new release is planned in April 2024. At the end of the ODISSEI roadmap project a stable version of the Portal should be available, yet the Portal functionalities will continue to be developed in other projects in particular in SSHOC-NL - [a collaboration between ODISSEI and CLARIAH](#) that started in January 2024.

The current version of the ODISSEI Portal is available at: <https://portal.odissei.nl/>.

DANS Data Station SSH

The [DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities](#) (SSH) is one of the digital repository services that DANS offers. The DANS Data Station SSH is one of four DANS Data Stations which have been developed in the last years to replace EASY, the trustworthy digital repository (TDR) that DANS was running for many years. More background on the transition is outlined in our strategy [Focus op FAIR: programma 2021-2025](#). The Data Station SSH was [launched in June 2023](#) and researchers wanting to archive and publish or search for SSH data archived at DANS have been able to make use of the many [new features and advantages](#) that this service offers compared to its predecessor EASY.

The Data Station SSH is one of the core services of DANS and will be developed and improved continuously through DANS-internal funding as well as through (inter)national projects. In particular,

we want the system to be aligned and integrated with the rest of the Dutch research infrastructure as best as possible. This includes making metadata available in the ODISSEI Portal as well as through CLARIAH (e.g. the Media Suite) and connecting the Data Station to other research services to allow the transfer of data (e.g. from SURF research drive, or to the [SANE environment](#)).

The Data Station SSH is available at: <https://ssh.datastations.nl/>

Connection between the ODISSEI Portal and the DANS Data Station SSH

Commonalities and differences

The table below summarises the commonalities (in **black**) as well as the differences (in **greenblue** and **blue**) between the ODISSEI Portal and the Data Station SSH.

ODISSEI Portal	Data Station SSH
<p>Metadata search portal prototype for ODISSEI (soon including data access broker functionality)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prototype • No contracts with data providers or users • DANS committed to maintain after the project for five years 	<p>Trustworthy Digital Repository service of DANS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service with user contracts • CoreTrustSeal awaiting • Sustainability is ensured (KNAW/NWO)
<p>To find datasets and their variables</p> <p>from various providers [DANS Data Station SSH (set of SS data), DataverseNL (set of SS data), CBS, LISS Panel, HSN, ...]</p>	<p>To find datasets and to deposit datasets</p> <p>in the Data Station SSH</p>
<p>Focus on the social sciences</p>	<p>Focus on the social sciences and humanities</p>
<p>You can find metadata only (harvested)</p> <p>Metadata from all providers is mapped to Dataverse standard metadata blocks and provider specific blocks</p>	<p>You can find metadata and data</p> <p>Metadata blocks are based on Dataverse standard metadata blocks and DANS specific blocks</p>
<p>+ Experimental metadata enrichments (e.g. add <i>ELSS</i> terms)</p> <p>- No search in the data itself</p>	<p>- No experimental enrichments</p> <p>+ Allows Full text search in data</p> <p>+ Features some information which is not available in the Portal (e.g. file information, access levels)</p>
<p>Developed by DANS (mostly) within project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ODISSEI partners have a voice in development 	<p>Developed by DANS as a DANS Service</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DANS solely responsible, consulting the community

Maintained by DANS (mostly) within project <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Systems + R&D team 	Maintained by DANS as a DANS Service <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core Development team + Functioneel Beheer
Uses Dataverse (Using Docker; Azure)	Uses Dataverse (Not Docker; KNAW servers)

Both the Data Station SSH and the ODISSEI Portal can be used to find social sciences datasets and access their metadata. Both are using Dataverse software and both are (mostly) developed and maintained by DANS.

The Portal is a metadata search portal that aggregates metadata from several providers (including but not limited to DANS). The Portal is developed within a project and is used to test and experiment with metadata enrichments and innovative search functionalities. The Portal is not a formal service of DANS in the sense that no contractual arrangements are in place between DANS and the data providers, and its development is driven by budget available in projects.

The Data Station SSH, on the other hand, is a repository service from DANS where datasets can be archived and published. In contrast to the ODISSEI Portal, searching for datasets is only a small part of the larger service of the Data Station SSH. The Data Station SSH is an official service of DANS that is governed by various contracts and is undergoing certification procedures (e.g. CoreTrustSeal). DANS receives structural funding for its archiving services and has contractual agreements to ensure the sustainability of the service.

In summary, although the Portal and the Data Station share data discovery features, they differ in key aspects and fulfil complementary functions. They should be seen as two separate but connected applications.

The next section outlines how both will be developed and maintained and how functionalities could become more closely integrated in the future.

Developments and future directions

Development and maintenance

The Data Station SSH is one of the core services of DANS which will be developed and maintained by DANS both through internal funding as well as through projects which have been acquired to work on specific features.

The Portal will be further developed within the ODISSEI Roadmap project until the end of 2024. At the end of 2024, a stable version of the Portal should be released. After this, as stated in the ODISSEI roadmap grant application, DANS has committed to maintain the Portal between 2025-2029. This means that the Portal will remain available with the features and metadata that has been included by the end of 2024. New developments can be added to the Portal if funding is available from additional projects or other sources. Several projects have started which also include components regarding data discovery and search and portal functionalities (e.g. SSHOC-NL, OpenQUAL) and it will be useful to align the Portal developments to these other projects. In fact, it is conceivable that the Portal will be adapted or integrated with new solutions as they emerge. This will at the time of course be discussed with the ODISSEI team. It is important to have some flexibility in the development of the Portal so we can develop and adjust the Portal based on how functionalities can best be achieved. Components (e.g. the Metadata ingest, Data Access Broker) should be designed with this in mind.

Distinguished look and feel

The similarities in look and feel of the Data Station and the Portal due to the use of the same software (Dataverse) has shown to be confusing to our community in understanding that they are distinct services. This should be addressed in the future. One simple step which is already planned is creating a more distinguished look for the Portal in the next release (April 2023).

Unfortunately, so far the Dataverse architecture had limited possibilities to tailor the front-end to achieve a substantially different look and feel for each service. However, new developments in the software (see next section) may allow for more flexibility in the future which will make it easier to create a unique look and feel for the Portal (and the Data Station).

Dataverse: separating components for search and archiving

In the current Dataverse software the data archiving functionalities and the search functionalities are integrated. This has been a disadvantage for us using Dataverse for the Portal where data archiving aspects of the software are not needed.

However, Dataverse has planned a new release where the different components are separated. Although the exact details of the new release remain unknown to this point, through this change, it should become easier to customise search functionalities without affecting the Dataverse infrastructure related to the data archiving functionalities. This should allow for more flexibility in developing and tailoring the metadata presentation and search functionalities which would significantly improve our ability to create a search interface tailored to the users needs.

This separation allows us to further innovate the discovery services ODISSEI and DANS offer. It is conceivable that we can in the future provide one search application which can show results based on user preferences. Results could then be adjusted to show studies relevant for ODISSEI users or to show the data available at DANS based on the same underlying metadata information.

In particular, if we are able to create a system that combines the unique search features from both the Portal (i.e. the metadata enrichments) and the Data Station (i.e. ability to include full text search results), it can become desirable to guide all users searching for data through one system.

How exactly this would be technically implemented and how this would relate to other existing search applications (e.g. in the humanities domain) are still open questions which will need to be addressed and depend on developments in projects (e.g. SSHOC-NL) and in the landscape in general.

In all cases, the Data Station SSH will remain the core service to deposit data and likely some kind of facility to discover data stored at DANS will also be offered.

The role of the data providers

The Portal has been developed to aggregate metadata from different data providers. DANS is one of those providers with a special role as we are also developing and maintaining the Portal. Yet the Portal also depends on the other data providers who need to be considered when discussing the future of the Portal and new developments. The data providers will need to ensure that their metadata is made available for the Portal in the future which requires investment from their side. Although the Portal is designed to require little work from the data providers once a harvesting mechanism is available, ideally the providers play an active role in shaping the development of new features and improvements to the Portal.

Crucially, the Portal was always meant to be a metadata aggregator and a broker, collecting and connecting services that exist within the infrastructure. The data always remains with the data providers and they are the ones responsible for managing their metadata and data according to the community standards.

The Portal does include metadata enrichments which are in many cases experimental features and are indicated as enrichments performed by the Portal to the user. In the future, we want to assess how

these enrichments could be used by the data providers to enrich the metadata stored within their own systems.

Since the Portal has this aggregation function, we have been strict in including metadata only if they comply with certain minimal requirements. Metadata needed to be harvestable from the provider and a Persistent Identifier (PID) needed to be in place. Through the PID users can be redirected to the original entries at the data providers.

This is also the reason why the Portal does not allow individual metadata entries for datasets from providers who do not have their own system for metadata publication and assignments of PIDs. In some cases we have referred those providers to existing services such as DANS, but a definite solution for registering metadata-only entries has not been established. Offering this would require a stable service and a clear agreement on the responsibilities (e.g. who is responsible for the DOIs and for the correctness of the metadata) to ensure it can be maintained sustainably. Importantly, offering publication of metadata without a way to ensure that data access is actually guaranteed could give the impression that the data is FAIR when in fact it may not.

The special role of CBS

We have made one exception to our requirements concerning the metadata provided by CBS. The metadata of the data designs from CBS describing the available microdatasets within the CBS remote access environment were not available to the public and CBS did not have a system in place to assign PIDs. The metadata is however very rich and was available in an internal system.

Due to the importance of the CBS microdata for the Dutch social sciences community, DANS has agreed to mint DOIs for the CBS metadata records of the data designs. This allows the metadata records to be included in the Portal and to be citable. The landing page of the DOIs was set to redirect to the Portal. This was established as a temporary solution with the intention for CBS to take over the DOIs at a given point in time so they can host the landing pages themselves and take over the responsibility for maintaining the information.

It is important to state that also in this case, CBS as the data provider is responsible to manage the metadata records and ensure that records which have been published and assigned a DOI remain accessible. Currently the publication of the CBS metadata is dependent on the Portal because the landing pages of the DOIs redirect to the metadata records on the Portal. This is an undesirable solution for the long term because it makes the data provider dependent on the Portal infrastructure which - as outlined above - is subject to project funding and should remain flexible so we can develop and adjust it based on how functionalities can best be achieved.

In Summary

The ODISSEI Portal and the DANS Data Station SSH should be seen as separate but connected applications. Both feature data discovery functionalities but only the Data Stations offers data archiving. The data discovery and data archiving functionality which are currently integrated in the Dataverse software will be separated into separate components in the future which will provide new opportunities for us to customise the search and metadata discovery.

The Portal has an aggregation and brokering function connecting existing services within the landscape. The Portal therefore depends on input from the data providers who remain responsible for managing their metadata and data according to the community standards. From the data providers, CBS has a special position as the metadata that is included in the ODISSEI Portal is not otherwise available and the related DOIs are temporally created through DANS. Besides this, we strive to minimise dependencies on specific features of the Portal as much as possible to allow for flexibility to achieve desired functionalities now and in the future.